

Satellite Data (NRSC)

SPOT IMAGE

Scene Parameters

Part 2 of 3

CST 551
August 1996

Produced at Manchester Computing in accordance with an agreement between the Combined Higher Education Software Team (CHEST) and National Remote Sensing Centre Ltd. (NRSC)/SPOT IMAGE.

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Preface to the Manchester Reprint

This document is a straight reprint of the manual produced by National Remote Sensing Centre Ltd. (NRSC) and SPOT IMAGE.

We are grateful to NRSC and SPOT IMAGE for permission to reproduce this manual for the higher education and research community in the U.K.

Reprinted at Manchester Computing, University of Manchester.

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PART 2

CD-ROM Directories

In order of appearance

CD Number : 7000005513
 Order Number : 95052327
 Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
 IMAGE

Date : 2-JUN-1995 08:08:43

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	01	Scene std.	1 013-234 88/04/04 11:48:05 1 P Level 1B SAT 0 ✓
2	02	Scene std.	1 013-235 88/04/04 11:48:13 1 P Level 1B SAT 0 ✓
3	03	Scene std.	1 018-227 88/09/03 11:24:35 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
4	04	Scene std.	1 018-229 88/08/28 11:40:16 1 P Level 1B SAT 0 ✓
5	05	Scene std.	1 021-233 88/10/15 11:17:43 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
6	06	Scene std.	1 021-235 88/10/15 11:17:59 2 P Level 1B SAT 0 ✓
7	07	Scene std.	1 021-236 88/10/31 11:10:28 2 P Level 1B SAT 0 ✓
8	08	Scene std.	1 022-236 89/03/15 11:14:03 1 P Level 1B SAT 0 ✓
9	09	Scene std.	1 025-237 89/05/05 11:33:14 2 P Level 1B SAT 0 ✓
10	10	Scene std.	1 025-238 89/07/06 11:41:23 2 P Level 1B SAT 0 ✓

X

X

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

CD Number : 7000005715
Order Number : 95052327
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

Date : 8-JUN-1995 13:49:25

S P O T
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CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	11	Scene std.	1 025-238 89/12/04 11:38:09 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	12	Scene std.	1 013-231 90/04/07 11:52:24 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	13	Scene std.	1 013-232 90/04/07 11:52:32 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
4	14	Scene std.	2 013-233 90/04/04 12:00:27 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
5	15	Scene std.	1 014-230 93/04/28 12:06:28 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
6	16	Scene std.	1 014-231 93/04/28 12:06:36 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
7	17	Scene std.	1 014-232 93/04/28 12:06:45 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
8	18	Scene std.	1 014-233 93/04/28 12:06:53 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
9	19	Scene std.	1 014-234 93/04/28 12:07:01 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
10	20	Scene std.	1 014-235 93/04/28 12:07:10 1 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

CD Number : 7000005870
Order Number : 95052327
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 21-JUN-1995 11:30:46

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	21	Scene std.	1 014-236 93/04/28 12:07:18 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	22	Scene std.	2 017-230 94/04/25 12:00:00 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	23	Scene std.	2 017-231 93/11/10 11:52:26 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
4	24	Scene std.	2 017-232 90/05/01 11:40:58 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
5	25	Scene std.	2 017-233 93/06/27 12:09:35 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
6	26	Scene std.	2 017-234 90/05/01 11:41:14 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
7	27	Scene std.	2 017-235 94/05/23 11:22:03 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
8	28	Scene std.	2 017-236 94/05/23 11:22:11 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
9	29	Scene std.	2 017-237 94/03/26 11:37:50 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
10	30	Scene std.	2 018-231 90/10/30 11:41:34 1 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

CD Number : 7000005917
Order Number : 95052327
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 23-JUN-1995 13:43:36

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	31	Scene std.	2 018-232 90/05/01 11:40:56 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	32	Scene std.	2 018-233 90/05/01 11:41:04 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	33	Scene std.	2 018-234 90/05/01 11:41:12 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
4	34	Scene std.	2 018-235 91/05/05 11:45:21 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
5	35	Scene std.	2 018-236 91/05/05 11:45:29 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
6	36	Scene std.	2 018-237 91/05/05 11:45:37 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
7	37	Scene std.	2 021-232 93/11/05 11:48:39 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
8	38	Scene std.	2 021-234 91/02/22 11:30:14 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
9	39	Scene std.	2 021-236 94/01/28 11:33:36 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
10	40	Scene std.	2 021-237 94/02/02 11:37:37 1 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

CD Number : 7000005749
Order Number : 95052327
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

Date : 14-JUN-1995 16:30:39

S P O T
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CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	41	Scene std.	3 021-238 94/02/22 11:11:06 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	42	Scene std.	3 022-238 94/02/17 11:07:10 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	43	Scene std.	2 018-229 94/04/25 11:59:52 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
4	44	Scene std.	2 018-238 91/05/05 11:45:46 1 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 4

PART 2

Work order : 9505232701
 CD number : 7000005513
 Scene ID : 1 13-234 88/04/04 11:48:05 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 1-JUN-1995 16:52:45

S P O T
 I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 13-234 88/04/04 11:48:05 1 P
 K-J identification 13-234
 Date 88/04/04
 Time 11 h 48 mn 05 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 015.6 Degres
 Incidence angle R02.3 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +166.6 Elevation: 038.1
 Gain Number 5
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.97559

Number of lines 5999
 Number of pixels per line 6232
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N056°53'21"
 Longitude W006°49'16"
 Pixel number 3120
 Line number 2998

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N057°13'04"	W007°08'59"	223	1
2	N057°04'19"	W006°11'39"	6232	1
3	N056°42'12"	W007°26'35"	1	5999
4	N056°33'34"	W006°29'59"	6010	5999

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6000	5999
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232702
 CD number : 7000005513
 Scene ID : 1 13-235 88/04/04 11:48:13 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 1-JUN-1995 16:58:12

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Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 13-235 88/04/04 11:48:13 1 P
 K-J identification 13-235
 Date 88/04/04
 Time 11 h 48 mn 13 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 015.4 Degres
 Incidence angle R02.3 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +166.2 Elevation: 038.5
 Gain Number 5
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.97559

Number of lines 5999
 Number of pixels per line 6235
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N056°25'50"
 Longitude W007°05'08"
 Pixel number 3122
 Line number 2998

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N056°45'31"	W007°24'43"	227	1
2	N056°36'52"	W006°28'02"	6235	1
3	N056°14'37"	W007°41'58"	1	5999
4	N056°06'06"	W006°45'59"	6009	5999

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6000	5999
Traller file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232703
CD number : 7000005513
Scene ID : 1 18-227 88/09/03 11:24:35 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 1-JUN-1995 16:53:19

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 18-227 88/09/03 11:24:35 1 P
K-J identification 18-227
Date 88/09/03
Time 11 h 24 mn 35 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 014.7 Degres
Incidence angle R13.1 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +167.2 Elevation: 036.9
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.96883

Number of lines 5987
Number of pixels per line 6527
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N060°03'40"
Longitude W001°36'41"
Pixel number 3292
Line number 2992

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N060°23'26"	W002°00'48"	213	1
2	N060°14'43"	W000°54'33"	6527	1
3	N059°52'29"	W002°18'57"	1	5987
4	N059°43'54"	W001°13'39"	6315	5987

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5988	5987
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232704
 CD number : 7000005513
 Scene ID : 1 18-229 88/08/28 11:40:16 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 1-JUN-1995 17:01:07

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Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 18-229 88/08/28 11:40:16 1 P
 K-J identification 18-229
 Date 88/08/28
 Time 11 h 40 mn 16 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 017.6 Degres
 Incidence angle L01.9 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +170.0 Elevation: 040.3
 Gain Number 5
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.96883

Number of lines 6001
 Number of pixels per line 6217
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N059°09'43"
 Longitude W002°27'00"
 Pixel number 3104
 Line number 3000

Corners Location

Comer	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N059°29'48"	W002°46'43"	205	1
2	N059°19'58"	W001°46'12"	6217	1
3	N058°59'15"	W003°07'20"	1	6001
4	N058°49'34"	W002°07'37"	6013	6001

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6002	6001
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232705
CD number : 7000005513
Scene ID : 1 21-233 88/10/15 11:17:43 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 1-JUN-1995 17:06:11

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Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 21-233 88/10/15 11:17:43 2 P
K-J identification 21-233
Date 88/10/15
Time 11 h 17 mn 43 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 012.5 Degres
Incidence angle R18.9 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +169.7 Elevation: 023.5
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.94798

Number of lines 5982
Number of pixels per line 6891
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N057°20'47"
Longitude W002°33'06"
Pixel number 3490
Line number 2989

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N057°40'16"	W002°58'32"	233	1
2	N057°32'26"	W001°53'20"	6891	1
3	N057°09'01"	W003°13'18"	1	5982
4	N057°01'19"	W002°08'57"	6659	5982

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5983	5982
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232706
CD number : 7000005513
Scene ID : 1 21-235 88/10/15 11:17:59 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 1-JUN-1995 17:01:24

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Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 21-235 88/10/15 11:17:59 2 P
K-J identification 21-235
Date 88/10/15
Time 11 h 17 mn 59 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 012.3 Degres
Incidence angle R18.9 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +169.3 Elevation: 024.3
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.94798

Number of lines 5983
Number of pixels per line 6896
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N056°25'50"
Longitude W002°59'18"
Pixel number 3491
Line number 2990

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N056°45'15"	W003°24'16"	239	1
2	N056°37'36"	W002°20'36"	6896	1
3	N056°13'59"	W003°38'27"	1	5983
4	N056°06'25"	W002°35'36"	6658	5983

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5984	5983
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232707
 CD number : 7000005513
 Scene ID : 1 21-236 88/10/31 11:10:28 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 1-JUN-1995 17:22:03

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Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 21-236 88/10/31 11:10:28 2 P
 K-J identification 21-236
 Date 88/10/31
 Time 11 h 10 mn 28 s
 Instrument HRV2
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 010.5 Degres
 Incidence angle R26.5 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +168.3 Elevation: 019.1
 Gain Number 5
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.94798

Number of lines 5971
 Number of pixels per line 7634
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N055°58'15"
 Longitude W003°07'02"
 Pixel number 3888
 Line number 2984

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N056°17'35"	W003°36'26"	247	1
2	N056°10'16"	W002°26'12"	7634	1
3	N055°46'10"	W003°48'48"	1	5971
4	N055°38'55"	W002°39'29"	7388	5971

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5972	5971
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232708
CD number : 7000005513
Scene ID : 1 22-236 89/03/15 11:14:03 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 1-JUN-1995 17:20:52

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Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 22-236 89/03/15 11:14:03 1 P
K-J identification 22-236
Date 89/03/15
Time 11 h 14 mn 03 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 012.2 Degres
Incidence angle R17.9 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +161.6 Elevation: 030.0
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.95530

Number of lines 5984
Number of pixels per line 6827
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N055°58'15"
Longitude W002°02'47"
Pixel number 3453
Line number 2990

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N056°17'37"	W002°27'03"	245	1
2	N056°10'03"	W001°24'50"	6827	1
3	N055°46'21"	W002°41'07"	1	5984
4	N055°38'52"	W001°39'42"	6583	5984

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5985	5984
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232709
CD number : 7000005513
Scene ID : 1 25-237 89/05/05 11:33:14 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 1-JUN-1995 17:22:41

S P O T

IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 25-237 89/05/05 11:33:14 2 P
K-J Identification 25-237
Date 89/05/05
Time 11 h 33 mn 14 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 016.8 Degres
Incidence angle L07.0 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +168.5 Elevation: 050.1
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.93956

Number of lines 6005
Number of pixels per line 6308
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N055°30'36"
Longitude W001°47'09"
Pixel number 3138
Line number 3002

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N055°50'35"	W002°05'38"	221	1
2	N055°41'04"	W001°09'58"	6308	1
3	N055°19'53"	W002°23'44"	1	6005
4	N055°10'30"	W001°28'43"	6088	6005

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6006	6005
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232710
CD number : 7000005513
Scene ID : 1 25-238 89/07/06 11:41:23 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 1-JUN-1995 17:21:24

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 25-238 89/07/06 11:41:23 2 P
K-J identification 25-238
Date 89/07/06
Time 11 h 41 mn 23 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 018.4 Degres
Incidence angle L16.5 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +167.1 Elevation: 057.3
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.92441

Number of lines 6012
Number of pixels per line 6703
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N055°02'52"
Longitude W001°48'49"
Pixel number 3314
Line number 3005

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N055°23'29"	W002°07'41"	215	1
2	N055°12'21"	W001°09'35"	6703	1
3	N054°53'02"	W002°27'04"	1	6012
4	N054°42'04"	W001°29'38"	6489	6012

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6013	6012
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

SPOT 1 HRV 1 013-234 04 APR 88
P

N56°53' / W006°49' 02°R 11H 48MN 05S N1B
ST042198 CCTCONTROL @CNES1988

SPOT 1 HRV 1 013-235 04 APR 88
P

N56°26' / W007°05' 02°R 11H 48MN 13S N18
ST042196 CCTCONTROL @CNES1988

SPOT 1 HRV 1 018-229 28 AUG 88
P

N59°10' / W002°27' 01"L 11H 40MN 16S N1B
ST042393 CCTCONTROL @CNES1988

SPOT1 HRV2 021-235/0 15 OCT 88
P

N56°26' / W002°59' 18°R 11H 17MN 59S N1B
52418014 CCTCONTROL @CNES1988

BNA 08461

SPOT1 HRV2 021-236/0 31 OCT 88
P

N55°58'W003°07' 26°R 11H 10MN 285 N1B
52418015 CCTCONTROL @CNES1988

BNA 08669

SPOT1 HRV1 022-236/0 15 MAR 89
P

N55°58'W002°03' 17°R 11H 14MN 035 N1B
52510005 CCTCONTROL @CNES1989

BNA 00113

BnA 8050

SPOT1 HRV2 025-237/0 05 MAY 89
P

N55°31' / W001°47' 06"L 11H 33MN 14S N1B
BMA08050 CCTCONTROL @CNES1989

SPOT1 HRV2 025-238/0 06 JUL 89
P

N55°03' / W001°49' 16"L 11H 41MN 23S N1B
BMA00706 CCTCONTROL @CNES1989

BMA00706

CD Number : 7000005715
Order Number : 95052327
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 8-JUN-1995 13:49:25

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	11	Scene std.	1 025-238 89/12/04 11:38:09 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	12	Scene std.	1 013-231 90/04/07 11:52:24 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	13	Scene std.	1 013-232 90/04/07 11:52:32 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
4	14	Scene std.	2 013-233 90/04/04 12:00:27 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
5	15	Scene std.	1 014-230 93/04/28 12:06:28 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
6	16	Scene std.	1 014-231 93/04/28 12:06:36 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
7	17	Scene std.	1 014-232 93/04/28 12:06:45 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
8	18	Scene std.	1 014-233 93/04/28 12:06:53 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
9	19	Scene std.	1 014-234 93/04/28 12:07:01 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
10	20	Scene std.	1 014-235 93/04/28 12:07:10 1 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

Work order : 9505232711
CD number : 7000005715
Scene ID : 1 25-238 89/12/04 11:38:09 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 8-JUN-1995 11:34:40

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 25-238 89/12/04 11:38:09 1 P
K-J identification 25-238
Date 89/12/04
Time 11 h 38 mn 09 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 017.0 Degres
Incidence angle L09.3 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +174.9 Elevation: 012.8
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.94008

Number of lines 6007
Number of pixels per line 6372
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N055°02'52"
Longitude W002°26'59"
Pixel number 3166
Line number 3003

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N055°22'57"	W002°45'20"	223	1
2	N055°13'12"	W001°49'49"	6372	1
3	N054°52'17"	W003°03'29"	1	6007
4	N054°42'40"	W002°08'37"	6150	6007

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6008	6007
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232712
CD number : 7000005715
Scene ID : 1 13-231 90/04/07 11:52:24 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 8-JUN-1995 11:35:13

S P O T

IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 13-231 90/04/07 11:52:24 1 P
K-J identification 13-231
Date 90/04/07
Time 11 h 52 mn 24 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 017.0 Degres
Incidence angle L01.9 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +169.3 Elevation: 037.8
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.94008

Number of lines 6002
Number of pixels per line 6217
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N058°15'25"
Longitude W006°01'00"
Pixel number 3105
Line number 3000

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N058°35'24"	W006°20'30"	211	1
2	N058°25'52"	W005°21'26"	6217	1
3	N058°04'46"	W006°40'07"	1	6002
4	N057°55'21"	W005°41'49"	6007	6002

Files parameters

Volume directory	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6003	6002
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232713
 CD number : 7000005715
 Scene ID : 1 13-232 90/04/07 11:52:32 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 8-JUN-1995 11:34:38

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 13-232 90/04/07 11:52:32 1 P
 K-J identification 13-232
 Date 90/04/07
 Time 11 h 52 mn 32 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 016.8 Degres
 Incidence angle L01.9 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +168.9 Elevation: 038.2
 Gain Number 5
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.94008

Number of lines 6002
 Number of pixels per line 6219
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N057°48'08"
 Longitude W006°18'39"
 Pixel number 3106
 Line number 3000

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N058°08'05"	W006°38'01"	213	1
2	N057°58'40"	W005°39'38"	6219	1
3	N057°37'24"	W006°57'12"	1	6002
4	N057°28'07"	W005°59'34"	6007	6002

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6003	6002
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232714
 CD number : 7000005715
 Scene ID : 2 13-233 90/04/04 12:00:27 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 8-JUN-1995 11:43:10

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 13-233 90/04/04 12:00:27 2 P
 K-J identification 13-233
 Date 90/04/04
 Time 12 h 00 mn 27 s
 Instrument HRV2
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 018.3 Degres
 Incidence angle L10.4 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +170.8 Elevation: 037.6
 Gain Number 6
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.30674

Number of lines 6007
 Number of pixels per line 6404
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N057°20'35"
 Longitude W006°34'57"
 Pixel number 3179
 Line number 3003

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N057°40'56"	W006°53'51"	209	1
2	N057°30'23"	W005°54'53"	6404	1
3	N057°10'30"	W007°14'15"	1	6007
4	N057°00'05"	W006°16'01"	6196	6007

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6008	6007
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232715
CD number : 7000005715
Scene ID : 1 14-230 93/04/28 12:06:28 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 8-JUN-1995 11:43:47

S P O T
I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 14-230 93/04/28 12:06:28 1 P
K-J identification 14-230
Date 93/04/28
Time 12 h 06 mn 28 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 021.8 Degres
Incidence angle L22.3 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +176.9 Elevation: 045.1
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.50967

Number of lines 6012
Number of pixels per line 7136
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N058°42'38"
Longitude W004°29'20"
Pixel number 3512
Line number 3005

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N059°04'17"	W004°49'56"	187	1
2	N058°50'15"	W003°42'47"	7136	1
3	N058°34'30"	W005°14'28"	1	6012
4	N058°20'41"	W004°08'06"	6950	6012

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6013	6012
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232716
 CD number : 7000005715
 Scene ID : 1 14-231 93/04/28 12:06:36 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 8-JUN-1995 11:43:06

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 14-231 93/04/28 12:06:36 1 P
 K-J identification 14-231
 Date 93/04/28
 Time 12 h 06 mn 36 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 021.5 Degres
 Incidence angle L22.3 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +176.4 Elevation: 045.6
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.50967

Number of lines 6012
 Number of pixels per line 7137
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N058°15'26"
 Longitude W004°51'52"
 Pixel number 3514
 Line number 3005

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N058°37'02"	W005°12'25"	189	1
2	N058°23'12"	W004°05'59"	7137	1
3	N058°07'11"	W005°36'21"	1	6012
4	N057°53'33"	W004°30'42"	6949	6012

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6013	6012
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232717
 CD number : 7000005715
 Scene ID : 1 14-232 93/04/28 12:06:45 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 8-JUN-1995 12:20:12

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID : 1 14-232 93/04/28 12:06:45 1 P
 K-J identification : 14-232
 Date : 93/04/28
 Time : 12 h 06 mn 45 s
 Instrument : HRV1
 Shift Along Track : 0
 Processing level : 1B
 Spectral mode : PAN
 Number of spectral bands : 1
 Spectral band indicators : PAN
 Orientation angle : 021.2 Degres
 Incidence angle : L22.3 Degres
 Sun angles (degrees) : Azimut: +175.9 Elevation: 046.0
 Gain Number : 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) : 01.50967

Number of lines : 6012
 Number of pixels per line : 7140
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record : byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude : N057°48'10"
 Longitude : W005°13'53"
 Pixel number : 3514
 Line number : 3005

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N058°09'42"	W005°34'22"	193	1
2	N057°56'03"	W004°28'39"	7140	1
3	N057°39'47"	W005°57'44"	1	6012
4	N057°26'21"	W004°52'47"	6948	6012

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6013	6012
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232718
 CD number : 7000005715
 Scene ID : 1 14-233 93/04/28 12:06:53 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 8-JUN-1995 12:20:04

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 14-233 93/04/28 12:06:53 1 P
 K-J identification 14-233
 Date 93/04/28
 Time 12 h 06 mn 53 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 020.9 Degres
 Incidence angle L22.3 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +175.4 Elevation: 046.5
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.50967

Number of lines 6012
 Number of pixels per line 7143
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N057°20'48"
 Longitude W005°35'24"
 Pixel number 3515
 Line number 3005

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N057°42'17"	W005°55'49"	197	1
2	N057°28'49"	W004°50'48"	7143	1
3	N057°12'19"	W006°18'39"	1	6012
4	N056°59'03"	W005°14'22"	6947	6012

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6013	6012
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232719
 CD number : 7000005715
 Scene ID : 1 14-234 93/04/28 12:07:01 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 8-JUN-1995 12:18:53

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 14-234 93/04/28 12:07:01 1 P
 K-J identification 14-234
 Date 93/04/28
 Time 12 h 07 mn 01 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 020.6 Degres
 Incidence angle 122.3 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +174.9 Elevation: 046.9
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.50967

Number of lines 6012
 Number of pixels per line 7145
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N056°53'22"
 Longitude W005°56'26"
 Pixel number 3517
 Line number 3005

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N057°14'47"	W006°16'47"	199	1
2	N057°01'30"	W005°12'27"	7145	1
3	N056°44'46"	W006°39'05"	1	6012
4	N056°31'40"	W005°35'29"	6947	6012

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6013	6012
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232720
CD number : 7000005715
Scene ID : 1 14-235 93/04/28 12:07:10 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 8-JUN-1995 12:23:21

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 14-235 93/04/28 12:07:10 1 P
K-J identification 14-235
Date 93/04/28
Time 12 h 07 mn 10 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 020.3 Degres
Incidence angle L22.3 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +174.5 Elevation: 047.4
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.50967

Number of lines 6012
Number of pixels per line 7148
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N056°25'52"
Longitude W006°17'01"
Pixel number 3518
Line number 3005

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N056°47'14"	W006°37'17"	203	1
2	N056°34'07"	W005°33'37"	7148	1
3	N056°17'09"	W006°59'05"	1	6012
4	N056°04'14"	W005°56'09"	6946	6012

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6013	6012
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

SPOT1 HRV1 013-231/0 07 APR 90
P

N58°15'/W006°01' 01°L 11H 52MN 24S N1B
BMA05796 CCTCONTROL 0CNES1990

BMA05796

SPOT1 HRV1 013-232/0 07 APR 90
P

N57°48' W006°19' 01°L 11H 52MN 325 N1B
BMA05775 CCTCONTROL @CNES1990

BMA05775

SPOT2 HRV2 013-233/0 04 APR 90
P

N57°21' W006°35' 10"L 12H 00MN 275 N1B
BMA05774 CCTCONTROL 0CNES1990

BMA05774

SPOT1 HRV1 014-230/0 28 APR 93
P

N58°43'W004°29' 22°L 12H 06MN 28S M1B
BMA06959 CCTCONTROL GCNES1993

BMA06959

SPOT1 HRV1 014-230/0 28 APR 93
P

◦ N58°43' / W004°29' 22°L 12H 06MN 285 N1B
BMA06959 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA06959

SPOT1 HRV1 014-231/0 28 APR 93

F

N58°15' / W004°52' 22°L 12H 06MN 36S N18
BMA06960 CCTCONTROL 0CNES1993

BMA06960

SPOT1 HRV1 014-232/0 28 APR 93
P

N57°48' / W005°14' 22°L 12H 06MN 45S N1B
BMA06961 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA06961

SPOT1 HRV1 014-233/0 28 APR 93
P

N57°21' / W005°35' 22°L 12H 06MN 53S N18
BMA06962 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA06962

SPOT1 HRV1 014-234/0 28 APR 93
P

N56°53' / W005°56' 22°L 12H 07MN 01S N1B
BMA06963 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA06963

SPOT1 HRV1 014-235/0 28 APR 93
P

N56°26' / W006°17' 22°L 12H 07MN 10S N1B
BMA06964 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA06964

CD Number : 7000005870
Order Number : 95052327
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 21-JUN-1995 11:30:46

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	21	Scene std.	1 014-236 93/04/28 12:07:18 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	22	Scene std.	2 017-230 94/04/25 12:00:00 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	23	Scene std.	2 017-231 93/11/10 11:52:26 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
4	24	Scene std.	2 017-232 90/05/01 11:40:58 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
5	25	Scene std.	2 017-233 93/06/27 12:09:35 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
6	26	Scene std.	2 017-234 90/05/01 11:41:14 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
7	27	Scene std.	2 017-235 94/05/23 11:22:03 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
8	28	Scene std.	2 017-236 94/05/23 11:22:11 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
9	29	Scene std.	2 017-237 94/03/26 11:37:50 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
10	30	Scene std.	2 018-231 90/10/30 11:41:34 1 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

Work order : 9505232721
 CD number : 7000005870
 Scene ID : 1 14-236 93/04/28 12:07:18 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 21-JUN-1995 09:54:04

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 14-236 93/04/28 12:07:18 1 P
 K-J identification 14-236
 Date 93/04/28
 Time 12 h 07 mn 18 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 020.1 Degres
 Incidence angle 122.3 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +174.0 Elevation: 047.8
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.50967

Number of lines 6012
 Number of pixels per line 7149
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N055°58'16"
 Longitude W006°37'10"
 Pixel number 3518
 Line number 3005

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N056°19'35"	W006°57'21"	205	1
2	N056°06'39"	W005°54'20"	7149	1
3	N055°49'27"	W007°18'40"	1	6012
4	N055°36'42"	W006°16'22"	6945	6012

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6013	6012
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232722
CD number : 7000005870
Scene ID : 2 17-230 94/04/25 12:00:00 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 21-JUN-1995 09:50:51

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 17-230 94/04/25 12:00:00 1 P
K-J Identification 17-230
Date 94/04/25
Time 12 h 00 mn 00 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 021.2 Degres
Incidence angle L19.6 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +176.2 Elevation: 044.2
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.65634

Number of lines 6011
Number of pixels per line 6904
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N058°42'38"
Longitude W003°16'09"
Pixel number 3404
Line number 3005

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N059°03'57"	W003°36'11"	189	1
2	N058°50'48"	W002°30'59"	6904	1
3	N058°34'02"	W004°00'04"	1	6011
4	N058°21'04"	W002°55'39"	6716	6011

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6012	6011
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232723
 CD number : 7000005870
 Scene ID : 2 17-231 93/11/10 11:52:26 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 21-JUN-1995 09:54:44

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 17-231 93/11/10 11:52:26 2 P
 K-J identification 17-231
 Date 93/11/10
 Time 11 h 52 mn 26 s
 Instrument HRV2
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 018.8 Degres
 Incidence angle L10.4 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +178.1 Elevation: 014.8
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.55618

Number of lines 6008
 Number of pixels per line 6397
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N058°15'26"
 Longitude W004°02'20"
 Pixel number 3176
 Line number 3003

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N058°35'53"	W004°21'26"	203	1
2	N058°25'04"	W003°21'08"	6397	1
3	N058°05'31"	W004°42'45"	1	6008
4	N057°54'52"	W003°43'12"	6195	6008

Files parameters

Volume directory	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6009	6008
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232724
 CD number : 7000005870
 Scene ID : 2 17-232 90/05/01 11:40:58 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 21-JUN-1995 09:53:46

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 17-232 90/05/01 11:40:58 1 P
 K-J identification 17-232
 Date 90/05/01
 Time 11 h 40 mn 58 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 016.1 Degres
 Incidence angle R02.3 Degres
 Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +168.3 Elevation: 046.6
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.39198

Number of lines 6000
 Number of pixels per line 6226
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N057°47'50"
 Longitude W004°16'05"
 Pixel number 3117
 Line number 2999

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N058°07'39"	W004°36'02"	215	1
2	N057°58'38"	W003°37'23"	6226	1
3	N057°36'51"	W004°54'29"	1	6000
4	N057°27'58"	W003°56'36"	6012	6000

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6001	6000
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232725
CD number : 7000005870
Scene ID : 2 17-233 93/06/27 12:09:35 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 21-JUN-1995 10:10:06

S P O T

IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 17-233 93/06/27 12:09:35 2 P
K-J identification 17-233
Date 93/06/27
Time 12 h 09 mn 35 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 021.9 Degres
Incidence angle 26.8 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +175.7 Elevation: 056.0
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.55618

Number of lines 6013
Number of pixels per line 7630
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N057°20'48"
Longitude W004°22'41"
Pixel number 3740
Line number 3006

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N057°42'56"	W004°44'32"	193	1
2	N057°27'51"	W003°35'25"	7630	1
3	N057°13'10"	W005°08'18"	1	6013
4	N056°58'18"	W003°59'57"	7438	6013

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6014	6013
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232726
 CD number : 7000005870
 Scene ID : 2 17-234 90/05/01 11:41:14 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 21-JUN-1995 10:07:22

S P O T
 I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 17-234 90/05/01 11:41:14 1 P
 K-J identification 17-234
 Date 90/05/01
 Time 11 h 41 mn 14 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 015.7 Degres
 Incidence angle R02.3 Degres
 Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +167.4 Elevation: 047.4
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.39198

Number of lines 6000
 Number of pixels per line 6230
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N056°53'02"
 Longitude W004°48'54"
 Pixel number 3120
 Line number 2999

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N057°12'47"	W005°08'35"	221	1
2	N057°03'59"	W004°11'17"	6230	1
3	N056°41'56"	W005°26'15"	1	6000
4	N056°33'15"	W004°29'40"	6010	6000

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6001	6000
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232727
CD number : 7000005870
Scene ID : 2 17-235 94/05/23 11:22:03 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 21-JUN-1995 10:10:53

S P O T

IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 17-235 94/05/23 11:22:03 1 P
K-J identification 17-235
Date 94/05/23
Time 11 h 22 mn 03 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 011.1 Degres
Incidence angle R24.1 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +158.4 Elevation: 052.6
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.65634

Number of lines 5974
Number of pixels per line 7371
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N056°25'51"
Longitude W005°14'01"
Pixel number 3748
Line number 2985

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N056°45'13"	W005°42'04"	245	1
2	N056°37'46"	W004°33'38"	7371	1
3	N056°13'51"	W005°55'09"	1	5974
4	N056°06'29"	W004°47'37"	7127	5974

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5975	5974
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232728
CD number : 7000005870
Scene ID : 2 17-236 94/05/23 11:22:11 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 21-JUN-1995 10:09:46

S P O T

IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 17-236 94/05/23 11:22:11 1 P
K-J identification 17-236
Date 94/05/23
Time 11 h 22 mn 11 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 011.0 Degres
Incidence angle R24.1 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +157.9 Elevation: 053.0
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.65634

Number of lines 5974
Number of pixels per line 7374
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N055°58'16"
Longitude W005°25'50"
Pixel number 3747
Line number 2985

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N056°17'36"	W005°53'36"	249	1
2	N056°10'14"	W004°45'58"	7374	1
3	N055°46'14"	W006°06'27"	1	5974
4	N055°38'56"	W004°59'42"	7126	5974

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5975	5974
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232729
CD number : 7000005870
Scene ID : 2 17-237 94/03/26 11:37:50 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 21-JUN-1995 10:47:22

S P O T

IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 17-237 94/03/26 11:37:50 1 P
K-J identification 17-237
Date 94/03/26
Time 11 h 37 mn 50 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 014.3 Degres
Incidence angle R06.3 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +164.5 Elevation: 035.3
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.65634

Number of lines 5997
Number of pixels per line 6300
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N055°30'37"
Longitude W005°31'02"
Pixel number 3163
Line number 2997

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N055°50'09"	W005°51'05"	235	1
2	N055°42'00"	W004°54'57"	6300	1
3	N055°19'06"	W006°07'00"	1	5997
4	N055°11'04"	W005°11'33"	6066	5997

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5998	5997
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232730
 CD number : 7000005870
 Scene ID : 2 18-231 90/10/30 11:41:34 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 21-JUN-1995 10:45:05

S P O T
 I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 18-231 90/10/30 11:41:34 1 P
 K-J identification 18-231
 Date 90/10/30
 Time 11 h 41 mn 34 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 016.9 Degres
 Incidence angle L01.2 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +176.2 Elevation: 018.1
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.37760

Number of lines 6002
 Number of pixels per line 6215
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N058°15'25"
 Longitude W003°12'41"
 Pixel number 3106
 Line number 3000

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N058°35'24"	W003°32'15"	209	1
2	N058°25'54"	W002°33'09"	6215	1
3	N058°04'44"	W003°51'46"	1	6002
4	N057°55'22"	W002°53'27"	6007	6002

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6003	6002
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

SPOT1 HRV1 014-236/0 28 APR 93
P

N55°58' / W006°37' 22°L 12H 07MN 18S N1B
BMA06967 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA06967

SPOT2 HRV1 017-230/0 25 APR 94
P

N58°43' / W003°16' 19"L 12H 00MN 00S N1B

BMA06968

CCTCONTROL @CNES1994

BMA06968

SPOT2 HRV2 017-231/0 10 NOV 93
P

N58°15' / W084°02' 10°L 11H 52MN 265 N1B
BMA06988 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA06988

SPOT2 HRV1 017-232/0 01 MAY 90
P

N57°48' W004°16' 02°R 11H 40MN 59S N1B
BMA06989 CCTCONTROL @CNES1990

BMA06989

SPOTZ HRVZ 017-233/0 27 JUN 93
P

N57°21'W004°23' 26°L 12H 09MN 355 N1B
BMA06990 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA06990

SPOT2 HRV1 017-234/0 01 MAY 90
P

N56°53' / W004°49' 02°R 11H 41MN 15S N1B
BMA06997 CCTCONTROL @CNES1990

BMA06997

SPOT2 HRV1 017-235/0 23 MAY 94
P

N56°26' / W005°14' 24°R 11H 22MN 03S N1B
BMA07000 CCTCONTROL @CNES1994

BMA 07000

SPOT2 HRV1 017-236/0 23 MAY 94
P

N55°58' / W005°26' 24°R 11H 22M 11S N1B
BMA07001 CCTCONTROL @CNES1994

BMA 07001

SPOTZ HRV1 017-237/0 26 MAR 94
-0

N55°31' / W005°31' 06°R 11H 37MN 50S N1B
BMA07002 CCTCONTROL @CNES1994

BMA07002

SPOT2 HRV1 018-231/0 30 OCT 90
P

N58°15' W083°13' 01°L 11H 41MN 34S N1B
BMA07004 CCTCONTROL @CNES1990

BMA07004

CD Number : 7000005917
Order Number : 95052327
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 23-JUN-1995 13:43:36

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	31	Scene std.	2 018-232 90/05/01 11:40:56 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	32	Scene std.	2 018-233 90/05/01 11:41:04 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	33	Scene std.	2 018-234 90/05/01 11:41:12 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
4	34	Scene std.	2 018-235 91/05/05 11:45:21 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
5	35	Scene std.	2 018-236 91/05/05 11:45:29 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
6	36	Scene std.	2 018-237 91/05/05 11:45:37 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
7	37	Scene std.	2 021-232 93/11/05 11:48:39 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
8	38	Scene std.	2 021-234 91/02/22 11:30:14 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
9	39	Scene std.	2 021-236 94/01/28 11:33:36 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
10	40	Scene std.	2 021-237 94/02/02 11:37:37 1 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

Work order : 9505232731
CD number : 7000005917
Scene ID : 2 18-232 90/05/01 11:40:56 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 23-JUN-1995 10:25:20

S P O T

IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 18-232 90/05/01 11:40:56 2 P
K-J Identification 18-232
Date 90/05/01
Time 11 h 40 mn 56 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 016.9 Degres
Incidence angle L02.2 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +169.7 Elevation: 046.7
Gain Number 6
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.29354

Number of lines 6003
Number of pixels per line 6228
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N057°47'58"
Longitude W003°15'14"
Pixel number 3110
Line number 3000

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N058°07'57"	W003°34'33"	213	1
2	N057°58'26"	W002°36'08"	6228	1
3	N057°37'17"	W003°53'52"	1	6003
4	N057°27'55"	W002°56'12"	6016	6003

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6004	6003
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232732
 CD number : 7000005917
 Scene ID : 2 18-233 90/05/01 11:41:04 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 23-JUN-1995 10:26:34

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID : 2 18-233 90/05/01 11:41:04 2 P
 K-J identification : 18-233
 Date : 90/05/01
 Time : 11 h 41 mn 04 s
 Instrument : HRV2
 Shift Along Track : 0
 Processing level : 1B
 Spectral mode : PAN
 Number of spectral bands : 1
 Spectral band indicators : PAN
 Orientation angle : 016.7 Degres
 Incidence angle : L02.2 Degres
 Sun angles (degrees) : Azimut: +169.3 Elevation: 047.1
 Gain Number : 6
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) : 01.29354

Number of lines : 6003
 Number of pixels per line : 6231
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record : byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude : N057°20'37"
 Longitude : W003°32'38"
 Pixel number : 3110
 Line number : 3000

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N057°40'33"	W003°51'50"	217	1
2	N057°31'10"	W002°54'05"	6231	1
3	N057°09'51"	W004°10'44"	1	6003
4	N057°00'36"	W003°13'42"	6015	6003

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6004	6003
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232733
 CD number : 7000005917
 Scene ID : 2 18-234 90/05/01 11:41:12 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 23-JUN-1995 10:25:20

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 18-234 90/05/01 11:41:12 2 P
 K-J identification 18-234
 Date 90/05/01
 Time 11 h 41 mn 12 s
 Instrument HRV2
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 016.5 Degres
 Incidence angle L02.2 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +168.8 Elevation: 047.5
 Gain Number 6
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.29354

Number of lines 6003
 Number of pixels per line 6232
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N056°53'10"
 Longitude W003°49'41"
 Pixel number 3111
 Line number 3000

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N057°13'04"	W004°08'46"	219	1
2	N057°03'48"	W003°11'40"	6232	1
3	N056°42'20"	W004°27'15"	1	6003
4	N056°33'12"	W003°30'52"	6014	6003

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6004	6003
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232734
CD number : 7000005917
Scene ID : 2 18-235 91/05/05 11:45:21 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 23-JUN-1995 10:40:06

S P O T

IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 18-235 91/05/05 11:45:21 1 P
K-J identification 18-235
Date 91/05/05
Time 11 h 45 mn 21 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 017.2 Degres
Incidence angle L06.6 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +169.8 Elevation: 049.3
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.36035

Number of lines 6006
Number of pixels per line 6295
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N056°25'51"
Longitude W004°07'13"
Pixel number 3133
Line number 3002

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N056°45'54"	W004°25'52"	217	1
2	N056°36'11"	W003°29'04"	6295	1
3	N056°15'16"	W004°44'46"	1	6006
4	N056°05'40"	W003°48'39"	6079	6006

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6007	6006
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232735
 CD number : 7000005917
 Scene ID : 2 18-236 91/05/05 11:45:29 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 23-JUN-1995 10:36:29

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 18-236 91/05/05 11:45:29 1 P
 K-J identification 18-236
 Date 91/05/05
 Time 11 h 45 mn 29 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 017.0 Degres
 Incidence angle L06.6 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +169.3 Elevation: 049.7
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.36035

Number of lines 6006
 Number of pixels per line 6296
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N055°58'15"
 Longitude W004°24'22"
 Pixel number 3134
 Line number 3002

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N056°18'17"	W004°42'56"	219	1
2	N056°08'40"	W003°46'44"	6296	1
3	N055°47'37"	W005°01'25"	1	6006
4	N055°38'08"	W004°05'54"	6078	6006

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6007	6006
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232736
CD number : 7000005917
Scene ID : 2 18-237 91/05/05 11:45:37 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 23-JUN-1995 10:41:49

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 18-237 91/05/05 11:45:37 1 P
K-J identification 18-237
Date 91/05/05
Time 11 h 45 mn 37 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 016.7 Degres
Incidence angle L06.6 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +168.8 Elevation: 050.1
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.36035

Number of lines 6006
Number of pixels per line 6297
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N055°30'36"
Longitude W004°41'12"
Pixel number 3136
Line number 3002

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N055°50'35"	W004°59'39"	221	1
2	N055°41'05"	W004°04'04"	6297	1
3	N055°19'53"	W005°17'45"	1	6006
4	N055°10'31"	W004°22'50"	6077	6006

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6007	6006
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232737
CD number : 7000005917
Scene ID : 2 21-232 93/11/05 11:48:39 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 23-JUN-1995 10:41:18

S P O T

IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 21-232 93/11/05 11:48:39 1 P
K-J identification 21-232
Date 93/11/05
Time 11 h 48 mn 39 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 019.5 Degres
Incidence angle L14.8 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +178.9 Elevation: 016.7
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.67126

Number of lines 6010
Number of pixels per line 6591
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N057°48'09"
Longitude W002°19'06"
Pixel number 3263
Line number 3004

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N058°08'53"	W002°38'20"	199	1
2	N057°57'20"	W001°37'10"	6591	1
3	N057°38'38"	W003°00'03"	1	6010
4	N057°27'15"	W001°59'38"	6393	6010

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
imagery file	8640	6011	6010
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232738
 CD number : 7000005917
 Scene ID : 2 21-234 91/02/22 11:30:14 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 23-JUN-1995 11:55:03

S P O T
 I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 21-234 91/02/22 11:30:14 1 P
 K-J identification 21-234
 Date 91/02/22
 Time 11 h 30 mn 14 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 014.8 Degres
 Incidence angle R06.3 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +165.4 Elevation: 021.6
 Gain Number 8
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.76453

Number of lines 5996
 Number of pixels per line 6296
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N056°53'21"
 Longitude W002°53'07"
 Pixel number 3161
 Line number 2997

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N057°12'58"	W003°13'41"	225	1
2	N057°04'33"	W002°15'33"	6296	1
3	N056°42'00"	W003°30'33"	1	5996
4	N056°33'42"	W002°33'09"	6072	5996

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5997	5996
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232739
 CD number : 7000005917
 Scene ID : 2 21-236 94/01/28 11:33:36 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 23-JUN-1995 11:55:50

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 21-236 94/01/28 11:33:36 1 P
 K-J identification 21-236
 Date 94/01/28
 Time 11 h 33 mn 36 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 015.0 Degres
 Incidence angle R03.6 Degres
 Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +166.8 Elevation: 014.9
 Gain Number 8
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.65634

Number of lines 5998
 Number of pixels per line 6255
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N055°58'16"
 Longitude W003°41'08"
 Pixel number 3133
 Line number 2998

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N056°17'54"	W004°00'48"	229	1
2	N056°09'26"	W003°04'32"	6255	1
3	N055°46'57"	W004°17'31"	1	5998
4	N055°38'36"	W003°21'57"	6027	5998

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5999	5998
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232740
CD number : 7000005917
Scene ID : 2 21-237 94/02/02 11:37:37 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 23-JUN-1995 11:55:31

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 21-237 94/02/02 11:37:37 1 P
K-J identification 21-237
Date 94/02/02
Time 11 h 37 mn 37 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 015.8 Degres
Incidence angle L01.9 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +167.3 Elevation: 016.8
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.65634

Number of lines 6002
Number of pixels per line 6235
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N055°30'37"
Longitude W003°45'28"
Pixel number 3114
Line number 3000

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N055°50'23"	W004°04'14"	227	1
2	N055°41'29"	W003°09'01"	6235	1
3	N055°19'33"	W004°21'31"	1	6002
4	N055°10'46"	W003°26'58"	6009	6002

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6003	6002
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

SPOT2 HRV2 018-232/0 01 MAY 90
P

N57°48' W003°15' 02"L 11H 40MN 56S N1B
EMA07006 CCTCONTROL @CNES1990

BMA07006

SPOT2 HRV2 018-233/0 01 MAY 90
P

N57°21'4003"33' 02"L 11H 41MN 045 N1B
BMA07009 CCTCONTROL @CNES1990

BMA07009

SPOT2 HRV2 018-234/0 01 MAY 90
P

N56°53'4003"50' 02°L 11H 41MN 12S N18
BMA07023 CCTCONTROL @CNES1990

BMA07023

SPOT2 HRV1 018-235/0 05 MAY 91
P

N55°26'W004°07' 06°L 11H 45MN 21S N1B
BMA07024 CCTCONTROL @CNES1991

BMA07024

SPOT2 HRV1 018-236/0 05 MAY 91
P

155°58' / 4004°24' 06°L 11H 45MN 29S N16
EMA07037 CCTCONTROL @CNES1991

BMA07037

SPOT2 HRV1 018-237/0 05 MAY 91
P

N55°31' / W004°41' 06°L 11H 45MN 37S N18
BMA07038 CCTCONTROL @CNES1991

BMA07038

SPOTZ HRV1 021-232/0 05 NOV 93
P

N57°48'W002°19' 14°L 11H 48MN 39S N1B
BMA07039 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA07039

SPOT2 HRV1 021-234/0 22 FEB 91
P

N56°53' W002°53' 06°R 11H 30MN 14S N1B
BMA07040 CCTCONTROL @CNES1991

BMA07040

SPOTZ HRV1 021-236/0 28 JAN 94
F

N55°58' / W003°41' 03"R 11H 33MN 36S N18
BMA07041 CCTCONTROL @CNES1994

BMA0704A

SPOT2 HRV1 021-237/0 02 FEB 94
P

N55°31' W003°45' 01"L 11H 37MN 37S N1B
BMA07042 CCTCONTROL 0CNES1994

BMA07042

CD Number : 7000005749
Order Number : 95052327
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

Date : 14-JUN-1995 16:30:39

S P O T
I M A G E

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	41	Scene std.	3 021-238 94/02/22 11:11:06 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	42	Scene std.	3 022-238 94/02/17 11:07:10 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	43	Scene std.	2 018-229 94/04/25 11:59:52 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
4	44	Scene std.	2 018-238 91/05/05 11:45:46 1 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 4

Work order : 9505232741
CD number : 7000005749
Scene ID : 3 21-238 94/02/22 11:11:06 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 15:34:51

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 3 21-238 94/02/22 11:11:06 1 P
K-J Identification 21-238
Date 94/02/22
Time 11 h 11 mn 06 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 009.7 Degres
Incidence angle R29.7 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +158.8 Elevation: 022.3
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.80574

Number of lines 5966
Number of pixels per line 8074
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N055°02'40"
Longitude W004°15'59"
Pixel number 4123
Line number 2980

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N055°21'56"	W004°47'20"	255	1
2	N055°14'50"	W003°34'32"	8074	1
3	N054°50'27"	W004°58'37"	1	5966
4	N054°43'24"	W003°46'45"	7820	5966

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5967	5966
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232742
CD number : 7000005749
Scene ID : 3 22-238 94/02/17 11:07:10 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 15:35:01

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 3 22-238 94/02/17 11:07:10 1 P
K-J identification 22-238
Date 94/02/17
Time 11 h 07 mn 10 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 009.5 Degres
Incidence angle R30.4 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +158.9 Elevation: 020.5
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.80574

Number of lines 5965
Number of pixels per line 8177
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N055°02'40"
Longitude W003°28'00"
Pixel number 4179
Line number 2980

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N055°21'56"	W003°59'57"	255	1
2	N055°14'51"	W002°46'09"	8177	1
3	N054°50'26"	W004°11'05"	1	5965
4	N054°43'25"	W002°58'14"	7923	5965

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5966	5965
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232743
CD number : 7000005749
Scene ID : 2 18-229 94/04/25 11:59:52 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 15:42:39

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 18-229 94/04/25 11:59:52 1 P
K-J identification 18-229
Date 94/04/25
Time 11 h 59 mn 52 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 021.5 Degres
Incidence angle L19.6 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +176.7 Elevation: 043.7
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.65634

Number of lines 6011
Number of pixels per line 6900
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N059°09'44"
Longitude W002°53'48"
Pixel number 3403
Line number 3005

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N059°31'07"	W003°13'53"	185	1
2	N059°17'46"	W002°07'58"	6900	1
3	N059°01'16"	W003°38'22"	1	6011
4	N058°48'07"	W002°33'14"	6716	6011

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6012	6011
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232744
CD number : 7000005749
Scene ID : 2 18-238 91/05/05 11:45:46 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 15:42:17

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 18-238 91/05/05 11:45:46 1 P
K-J identification 18-238
Date 91/05/05
Time 11 h 45 mn 46 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 016.5 Degres
Incidence angle 106.6 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +168.3 Elevation: 050.5
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.36035

Number of lines 6006
Number of pixels per line 6300
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N055°02'52"
Longitude W004°57'41"
Pixel number 3136
Line number 3002

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N055°22'49"	W005°16'02"	225	1
2	N055°13'27"	W004°21'03"	6300	1
3	N054°52'05"	W005°33'46"	1	6006
4	N054°42'50"	W004°39'26"	6076	6006

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6007	6006
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

SPOT3 HRV1 021-238/0 22 FEB 94
P

N55°03' W004°16' 29°R 11H 11MN 065 N1B
BMA07043 CCTCONTROL @CNES1994

BMA07043

SPOT3 HRV1 022-238/0 17 FEB 94
P

N55°03' W083°28' 30°R 11H 07MN 10S N1B
BMA07044 CCTCONTROL @CNES1994

BMA 07044

SPOT2 HRV1 018-229/0 25 APR 94
P

N59°10' W002°54' 19°L 11H 59M 52S N1B
BMA07045 CCTCONTROL @CNES1994

BMA07045

SPOT2 HRV1 018-238/0 05 MAY 91
P

N55°03' / W004°58' 06"L 11H 45MN 46S N1B
BMA07047 CCTCONTROL @CNES1991

BMA07047